

Deep Learning and emotion recognition for an E-Learning platform

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Abstract—Emotion recognition has become a crucial aspect of human-computer interaction, with applications ranging from healthcare to entertainment. This article discusses the significance of emotion recognition in human-computer interaction, with a focus on its potential application in E-Learning platforms. The traditional E-Learning experience lacks emotional feedback, and deep learning models like CNNs and RNNs can recognize emotions from facial expressions data. Integrating deep learning-based emotion recognition algorithms into E-Learning platforms can provide real-time insights into learners' emotions, enabling personalized interventions and adaptive content delivery. Additionally, deep learning models can help create emotionally engaging learning materials, fostering a more immersive and enjoyable learning experience. The benefits of integrating deep learning-based emotion recognition in E-Learning platforms are significant, including improved user experience, enhanced engagement, and personalized learning experiences. However, it is crucial to balance leveraging emotion recognition technology with respecting users' privacy and autonomy. Overall, this article highlights the potential of deep learning techniques for emotion recognition and their application in E-Learning platforms to revolutionize the way learners interact with online educational resources, fostering a more empathetic, adaptive, and effective learning environment.

Keywords—learning platform, learning experience, deep learning model, emotion recognition, Facial Expression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human emotions are crucial in learning and engagement, influencing motivation, attention, and memory. Recognizing and understanding learners' emotions can greatly enhance the effectiveness of educational platforms, particularly in E-Learning. Artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning techniques can now integrate emotion recognition capabilities into E-Learning platforms, promising to improve user experience and personalize learning content.

Traditional E-Learning platforms offer a one-size-fits-all approach, providing static content and assessments that fail to consider learners' diverse emotional responses. However, deep learning algorithms can recognize and respond to users' emotions, creating a more engaging and personalized learning experience.

Deep learning leverages large-scale neural networks to extract intricate patterns and representations from complex data. Neural networks can extract emotional cues from different modalities, such as facial expressions, speech, and

text, enabling the recognition and understanding of learners' emotions in real-time.

The integration of deep learning techniques for emotion recognition in E-Learning platforms can adapt the presentation of learning materials, provide tailored feedback, and adjust the pacing and difficulty levels of the content. This personalized approach can significantly enhance learner engagement, motivation, and overall learning outcomes.

This article explores the challenges associated with recognizing emotions from various modalities and examines state-of-the-art approaches that have shown promising results. The potential benefits of leveraging emotion recognition in E-Learning, including adaptive learning environments and emotion-aware feedback systems, are discussed. Emerging research areas in deep learning and emotion recognition for E-Learning platforms are also outlined.

By understanding and incorporating learners' emotional states, E-Learning platforms can usher in a new era of personalized and engaging education. The following sections of this article provide a comprehensive overview of deep learning for emotion recognition, highlighting its potential impact on E-Learning and the steps necessary to harness its benefits effectively.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

The conventional method of e-learning heavily relies on written communication between teachers and students. However, this approach has limitations in providing a comprehensive learning experience as it cannot effectively convey emotions. In contrast to physical classrooms, where students can express their thoughts and emotions using verbal and nonverbal cues, the traditional e-learning approach falls short in this regard.

Emotions play a critical role in the learning process as they significantly impact students' motivation, engagement, and retention of information. Therefore, it is essential to incorporate emotional intelligence into e-learning systems to enhance the quality of the learning experience and improve learning outcomes. By integrating mechanisms that enable the expression and recognition of emotions, e-learning can bridge the gap between face-to-face interactions and virtual learning environments. This integration will help students engage more deeply with the material and feel a stronger connection to their learning journey, leading to more effective learning experiences and better retention of knowledge.

The field of emotion recognition has gained significant attention in research, with numerous studies investigating

various modalities like speech, physiological signals, and facial expressions to detect emotions. Facial expressions, in particular, have proven to be an effective means of recognizing emotions, holding promise for emotion recognition in e-learning. However, the majority of existing studies in this domain have primarily concentrated on offline approaches that rely on pre-collected data. Such approaches are inadequate for real-time emotion recognition in online learning environments.

Identifying learner satisfaction and engagement in e-learning environments poses a significant challenge. The satisfaction of learners with their learning experience has a direct impact on their motivation and performance, making it crucial to measure accurately. However, traditional methods of measuring learner satisfaction, such as feedback forms or questionnaires, are subjective and may not truly reflect the learners' emotions. Therefore, there is a necessity to develop objective and precise measures to gauge learner satisfaction and engagement in e-learning environments.

Moreover, there is a dearth of research on real-time emotion recognition in e-learning using facial expressions, which presents an opportunity for further exploration. The development of a real-time emotion recognition system based on facial expressions could significantly enhance the quality of the learning experience in e-learning environments. Therefore, this study seeks to address this research gap by creating an online machine learning-based emotion recognition system that uses facial expressions to detect learners' emotions in real-time. To evaluate its ability to measure learner satisfaction and engagement, the system will be tested on a sample of learners in an e-learning environment.

III. RELATED WORD

Gürüler, Hüseyin et al. [1] proposed a new system that uses technology to detect how students are feeling based on their facial expressions. This way, teachers can understand how their students are doing and create a more interactive learning environment. The study used different computer programs to figure out the best way to detect emotions, and found that kNN and SVM were the most accurate.

The researchers [2] used a special computer program to detect emotions from students' facial expressions while they were watching videos or chatting with their teacher online. They found that measuring emotions in real-time can help teachers understand how students are feeling and create better ways to help them learn.

The study [3] conducted by Hassouneh Aya, A.M. Mutawa, and M. Murugappan aimed to develop an algorithm for real-time emotion recognition using virtual markers, facial landmarks, and EEG signals. The specific focus of the study was on two specific populations: physically disabled individuals and children with Autism.

To accomplish their goal, the researchers utilized a combination of computer vision techniques and EEG signal analysis. The algorithm incorporated Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) classifiers to classify six different facial emotions and EEG signals.

The proposed work [4] encompasses three main objectives: face detection, recognition, and emotion classification. To accomplish these objectives, the authors utilize OpenCV and Python programming, along with a dataset for training and evaluation purposes.

The article describes an experiment conducted to identify the emotions of multiple students. The deep learning algorithm is employed to analyze facial expressions and classify emotions in real-time. The results obtained from the experiment demonstrate the effectiveness and efficacy of the face analysis system in accurately recognizing and classifying emotions.

The researchers [5] put forward a facial expression recognition approach utilizing a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with a LeNet architecture. They combined three datasets, namely JAFFE, KDEF, and their own custom dataset, to create a comprehensive training dataset. The LeNet architecture was then trained on this merged dataset to classify different emotion states.

The researchers [6] proposed an approach of Facial Expression Recognition (FER) using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). This model created using CNN can be used to detect facial expressions in real time. The system can be used for analysis of emotions while users watch movie trailers or video lectures.

The paper [7] presents a system that can detect frontal faces and code them in real-time across seven dimensions. The system utilizes boosting techniques and SVM classifiers to improve performance and has been tested on a dataset of posed facial expressions. The system's outputs change smoothly over time, providing an automatic and unobtrusive way to code facial expression dynamics, which could be a valuable representation.

The paper [8] compares five different methods for real-time emotion recognition from facial images, focusing specifically on the four basic emotions of happiness, sadness, anger, and fear. Three of the approaches are based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), while the remaining two methods utilize conventional techniques using Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) features.

The five approaches compared in the study are as follows:

- AlexNet CNN: This method utilizes a CNN architecture known as AlexNet for emotion recognition from facial images.
- Affdex CNN: This approach employs a CNN model called Affdex for real-time emotion recognition.
- FER-CNN: Another CNN-based method, FER-CNN, is used for emotion recognition in this comparison.
- SVM using HOG features: This method utilizes Support Vector Machines (SVM) and extracts features using Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG).
- MLP artificial neural network using HOG features: The final approach is based on a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) artificial neural network that incorporates HOG features for emotion recognition.

This paper [9] proposes an innovative approach to analyze real-time video and images to recognize facial expressions and emotions. This system will improve the quality of teaching, training, mentoring, and consultation services by providing a solution to the traditional feedback procedure. Both teachers and learners can benefit from the calculated Concentration Index, resulting in improved teaching and learning experiences.

This article [10], we explore the use of a deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) for recognizing facial emotions in videos using Google's TensorFlow machine-learning library. We applied this technique to ten emotions from the Amsterdam Dynamic Facial Expression Set-Bath Intensity Variations (ADFES-BIV) dataset and tested it using two datasets.

The paper [11] presents an approach for real-time emotion recognition from facial expressions in live video. The method employs an automatic facial feature tracker, SVM classifier, and evaluates its accuracy in various scenarios. The results indicate the effectiveness of the approach and its potential for enhancing man-machine interfaces and related domains.

The goal of this research project [12] is to develop real-time predictive models that can accurately classify emotions from videos of educational workshop participants interacting with a robot. By combining two generalized models, Inception-v3 and ResNet-34, we were able to achieve improved prediction accuracy. To evaluate our approach, we applied these models to video data and analyzed the emotions predicted by participants' gender, activities, and tasks. Our statistical analyses revealed that female participants were more likely to display emotions across all activity types, and happiness was the most frequently predicted emotion regardless of gender. Notably, programming was the activity type with the most frequently analyzed emotions. These results demonstrate the potential for utilizing facial expressions to enhance teaching practices and better understand student engagement.

IV. FOUNDATIONAL CONCEPTS :

A. Recognition of emotion based on facial expressions :

Recognizing emotions based on facial expressions means figuring out how someone is feeling by looking at their face. Different facial movements and expressions show different emotions, like happiness, sadness, anger, fear, surprise, and disgust. Scientists use computer programs to help them recognize these emotions by looking at the person's face and figuring out which emotions they are showing. This can be helpful in many different areas, like psychology, computers, virtual reality, and robots. By understanding people's emotions, we can make machines that are better at interacting with humans and making us feel understood.

Facial expressions serve as a primary means of nonverbal communication for emotions, with different emotional states expressed through muscle movements and changes in facial features like eyebrows, eyes, nose, mouth, and overall facial dynamics. Emotion recognition based on facial expressions typically includes the following steps:

Face detection is a technology that helps computers find human faces in pictures or videos. This helps with things

like recognizing emotions or identifying people. The computer looks for certain patterns and features to find faces. Once a face is found, more information can be gathered like age or gender

Feature extraction in face detection means finding important parts of a face in pictures or videos that can help us tell faces apart from other things. These parts are used to help computers find and locate faces.

There are many different types of models, like CNNs, LSTMs, SVMs, Random Forests, RNNs, Transformers, and Ensemble Models. Each model is good at understanding emotions in different ways, like looking at faces or listening to speech. Scientists choose which model to use based on what kind of information they have and what they want to learn about emotions.

Training such emotion recognition systems requires labeled datasets where human experts annotate facial expressions with corresponding emotional labels. During training, algorithms learn patterns and correlations between extracted facial features and specific emotions.

Recognition of emotion based on facial expressions has applications in human-computer interaction, affective computing, psychology research, market research, and social robotics, aiding in understanding and responding to human emotions.

To detect and analyze facial expressions in e-learning, a pipeline is used that involves multiple steps. The process begins with the acquisition of data through images, followed by the use of face detection algorithms to locate and isolate faces in the data. Facial landmark detection is then used to identify key points, such as the eyes, nose, and mouth, enabling detailed analysis. Techniques like deep learning are used to extract features from these landmarks or the overall facial region. An emotion classification model, which can be based on SVMs, CNNs, or ensemble models, analyzes the features to assign emotion labels. These classified emotions can be further analyzed to provide insights and feedback to learners, linking emotions to learning experiences. The pipeline is integrated into the e-learning system for real-time emotion monitoring and personalized learning experiences based on facial expressions. The specifics of the process may vary depending on the application and technology used.

Fig. 1. The steps of emotion recognition using facial expression

V. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study aims to evaluate various approaches for recognizing emotions from facial expressions in order to determine the most effective method. The investigation involves examining different techniques and algorithms employed in this field and assessing their performance. Based on this analysis, we will develop a specialized Neural Network (NN) capable of accurately identifying emotions.

To enhance the performance of our NN, several factors will be considered, including data preparation methods, feature selection techniques, and network architecture. We will employ advanced techniques to fine-tune the model and ensure its effectiveness across diverse scenarios.

The ultimate objective of this research is to advance the technology used in emotion recognition by developing a more accurate and efficient system. This improvement can have significant applications in various domains such as human-computer interaction, E-Learning, virtual reality, and healthcare.

To summarize, this study involves comparing different methodologies for emotion recognition from facial expressions and leveraging this knowledge to create a specialized Neural Network. The primary goal is to enhance computers' ability to understand emotions from facial cues, thus fostering more reliable and effective technology for the future.

A. Data Set Description :

To conduct our research, we will utilize the primary dataset available at [\[DataSET\]](#). This dataset serves as the foundation for training and testing our models in our study of facial expressions. It includes folders representing various emotions such as Surprise, Anger, Happiness, Sadness, Neutral, Disgust, and Fear.

The dataset is organized into two main folders: Training and Testing. This division facilitates the configuration of models for end-users. The training set consists of 28,079 samples, while the testing set comprises 7,178 samples. Each sample consists of grayscale face images with dimensions of 48x48 pixels. Notably, the dataset ensures that the faces are automatically registered, resulting in more or less centered faces occupying a similar amount of space in each image.

It is important to acknowledge that this dataset was obtained from the "Challenges in Representation Learning: Facial Expression Recognition Challenge" competition. Pierre-Luc Carrier and Aaron Courville prepared the dataset as part of their ongoing research project. They kindly provided a preliminary version of the dataset to the workshop organizers for use in this contest.

B. VGG16 Model [13]:

VGG16 is a deep convolutional neural network architecture that was developed by the Visual Geometry Group (VGG) at the University of Oxford. It gained significant popularity and became one of the influential models in the field of computer vision after its introduction in the 2014 ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC).

The "VGG" in its name refers to the research group responsible for its creation, and "16" denotes the total number of layers in the network. VGG16 has a straightforward and uniform architecture, consisting of multiple convolutional layers, followed by fully connected layers. The architecture of VGG16 is deeper compared to previous models like AlexNet, and it has a larger number of trainable parameters.

The key characteristics of the VGG16 architecture include:

- Convolutional Layers: VGG16 has 13 convolutional layers, each using a small receptive field size of 3x3 pixels, and with a stride of 1 pixel. The number of filters increases with the depth of the network, starting from 64 filters in the first layer and doubling after each pooling layer.
- Max Pooling Layers: After every two convolutional layers, VGG16 includes a max pooling layer with a 2x2 pixel window and a stride of 2 pixels. Max pooling reduces the spatial dimensions and helps capture important features.
- Fully Connected Layers: The final three layers of VGG16 are fully connected layers. The first two fully connected layers consist of 4,096 neurons each, while the last layer, also known as the output layer, has 1,000 neurons corresponding to the 1,000 ImageNet classes at the time of its development.
- Activation Function: Throughout the network, VGG16 uses the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function, which helps introduce non-linearity and learn complex features.
- Softmax Output: The output layer of VGG16 employs a softmax activation function, allowing it to produce class probabilities for multi-class classification tasks.

VGG16 is known for its simplicity and uniformity in architecture, which has made it a widely adopted model for various computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and feature extraction. Although VGG16 has a high number of parameters and is computationally expensive to train, it has demonstrated strong performance and continues to serve as a benchmark for evaluating newer convolutional neural network architectures.

C. VGG19 Model [14]:

VGG19 is an extension of the VGG16 architecture, developed by the Visual Geometry Group (VGG) at the University of Oxford. It shares similar principles with VGG16 but has a deeper network architecture with 19 layers, hence the name "VGG19."

The key characteristics of the VGG19 architecture include:

- Convolutional Layers: VGG19 consists of 16 convolutional layers, with each layer using a 3x3 filter and a stride of 1 pixel. The number of filters increases with the depth of the network, starting from 64 filters in the first layer and doubling after each pooling layer.
- Max Pooling Layers: Similar to VGG16, VGG19 includes max pooling layers after every two convolutional layers. These pooling layers have a 2x2 window size and a stride of 2 pixels, effectively reducing the spatial dimensions and capturing important features.
- Fully Connected Layers: VGG19 has three fully connected layers at the end of the network. The first two fully connected layers contain 4,096 neurons each, while the last layer (output layer) consists of 1,000 neurons for classifying images.

into 1,000 different categories, as in the ImageNet dataset.

- **Activation Function:** VGG19 uses the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function throughout the network, which introduces non-linearity and helps learn complex features.
- **Softmax Output:** The output layer of VGG19 applies the softmax activation function, enabling it to produce class probabilities for multi-class classification tasks.

VGG19 retains the simplicity and uniformity of the VGG16 architecture, with an increased depth of 19 layers. This deeper architecture allows for more expressive feature representation but comes at the cost of increased computational complexity and memory requirements.

VGG19 has been widely used and has achieved notable performance in various computer vision tasks, including image classification, object detection, and feature extraction. While newer and more complex architectures have emerged since its introduction, VGG19 still serves as a benchmark and reference for evaluating the effectiveness of more recent deep neural networks.

D. ResNet50V2 Model [15]:

ResNet50V2 is a variant of the ResNet (Residual Network) architecture, which is a deep convolutional neural network widely used for image classification tasks. ResNet50V2 builds upon the original ResNet50 model and incorporates several improvements to enhance its performance and address some of the limitations.

The key characteristics of the ResNet50V2 architecture include:

- **Residual Blocks:** ResNet50V2 employs residual blocks, which introduce skip connections to enable the network to learn residual mappings effectively. These skip connections allow the gradient to flow more directly during training, mitigating the vanishing gradient problem and making it easier to train deeper networks.
- **Convolutional Layers:** ResNet50V2 consists of a stack of convolutional layers with different filter sizes. It has 50 convolutional layers in total, including residual blocks that contain multiple convolutional layers within them. The convolutional layers use small filter sizes, typically 3x3 or 1x1, to capture local and global features efficiently.
- **Bottleneck Architecture:** ResNet50V2 incorporates a bottleneck architecture in its residual blocks. A bottleneck layer consists of 1x1, 3x3, and 1x1 convolutional layers, reducing the computational complexity while maintaining representation power. This architecture is particularly useful when dealing with deeper networks.
- **Global Average Pooling:** Instead of using fully connected layers at the end of the network, ResNet50V2 applies global average pooling. This technique calculates the average value of each feature map across spatial dimensions, resulting in a fixed-length vector that represents the image's

features. Global average pooling reduces the number of parameters in the model and helps prevent overfitting.

- **Pre-Activation:** ResNet50V2 introduces pre-activation residual units, where batch normalization and activation functions are applied before the convolution operation. This modification helps to address the degradation problem in very deep networks, making it easier to train and improving performance.

ResNet50V2 achieves state-of-the-art performance in image classification tasks and has been widely adopted as a powerful backbone architecture for various computer vision applications. Its ability to effectively train deep networks and handle complex feature representations makes it a popular choice among researchers and practitioners.

E. EfficientNetB0 Model [16]:

EfficientNetB0 is a convolutional neural network architecture designed to achieve high performance while maintaining computational efficiency. It is part of the EfficientNet family of models developed by Google Brain researchers. EfficientNet models are known for their state-of-the-art performance across various computer vision tasks.

The key characteristics of the EfficientNetB0 architecture include:

- **Compound Scaling:** EfficientNetB0 introduces a compound scaling technique that uniformly scales the depth, width, and resolution of the network. This scaling allows the model to balance between increasing model capacity and computational efficiency. The scaling coefficients are determined using a compound coefficient ϕ , which controls the overall model size.
- **Mobile Inverted Residual Bottleneck (MBConv):** EfficientNetB0 uses a variant of the inverted residual block known as MBConv. MBConv employs depthwise separable convolutions, which split the convolution operation into a depthwise convolution followed by a pointwise convolution. This approach reduces the number of computations while maintaining representational power.
- **Depthwise Convolution:** EfficientNetB0 utilizes depthwise convolutions, where each input channel is convolved separately with its own set of filters. This technique significantly reduces the number of parameters and computational cost compared to traditional convolutions, making the model more efficient.
- **Width Expansion Factor:** EfficientNetB0 incorporates a width expansion factor ρ to control the number of channels in each layer. By adjusting this factor, the model can strike a balance between performance and efficiency.
- **Resolution:** EfficientNetB0 operates on input images of size 224x224 pixels, which is the standard input resolution for many image classification tasks. The resolution is carefully chosen to maintain compatibility with pretrained weights and benchmark datasets.

EfficientNetB0 achieves impressive performance on image classification benchmarks while being computationally efficient. Its compound scaling strategy, combined with depthwise separable convolutions and carefully controlled model size, enables efficient resource utilization without sacrificing accuracy. EfficientNetB0 serves as a strong baseline architecture for various computer vision applications, providing an optimal trade-off between model performance and computational efficiency.

F. EfficientNetB7 Model [17]:

EfficientNetB7 is a powerful convolutional neural network architecture that belongs to the EfficientNet family. It is one of the largest and most advanced models in the EfficientNet series, known for its exceptional performance in various computer vision tasks.

EfficientNetB7 incorporates a combination of depth-wise separable convolutions, squeeze-and-excitation blocks, and compound scaling to achieve a high level of accuracy while minimizing computational complexity. It has a significantly larger size and more parameters compared to its predecessors, allowing it to capture intricate patterns and representations in images with exceptional precision.

With its deep network architecture and sophisticated design, EfficientNetB7 is particularly well-suited for challenging visual recognition tasks, such as image classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation. It has demonstrated state-of-the-art performance on benchmark datasets and competitions, showcasing its effectiveness in handling complex visual data.

By leveraging EfficientNetB7, researchers and practitioners can benefit from its advanced capabilities to extract meaningful features from images and make accurate predictions. However, due to its larger size and increased computational requirements, it may be more suitable for scenarios where computational resources are more abundant.

EfficientNetB7 serves as a testament to the advancements in neural network architectures, pushing the boundaries of performance and accuracy in computer vision tasks. Its sophisticated design and superior performance make it a valuable asset for various applications in the field of deep learning and computer vision.

G. Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) :

Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is an optimization algorithm commonly used for training machine learning models, particularly in the field of deep learning. It is an iterative optimization technique that aims to minimize the loss function and find the optimal set of parameters for a given model.

The key characteristics of Stochastic Gradient Descent are as follows:

- **Gradient Estimation:** In SGD, the optimization process involves estimating the gradient of the loss function with respect to the model parameters. Instead of computing the gradient using the entire training dataset, SGD randomly samples a subset of training examples, known as a mini-batch, to

estimate the gradient. This mini-batch size is typically much smaller than the total training dataset.

- **Parameter Update:** After estimating the gradient, SGD updates the model parameters by taking a step in the direction of the negative gradient. The step size is controlled by the learning rate, which determines the magnitude of the update at each iteration. The learning rate is often set as a hyperparameter and can be fixed or adaptively adjusted during training.
- **Randomness:** SGD introduces randomness in the optimization process due to the random sampling of mini-batches. This randomness helps the algorithm escape local minima and explore different regions of the parameter space, potentially leading to better convergence and generalization.
- **Efficiency:** One of the main advantages of SGD is its efficiency. By using mini-batches, it can perform parameter updates more frequently compared to batch gradient descent, which processes the entire dataset in each iteration. This increased frequency of updates often leads to faster convergence and makes SGD suitable for large-scale datasets.
- **Noise Tolerance:** SGD's stochastic nature introduces some noise in the gradient estimates, which can act as a regularizer and help prevent overfitting. This noise has a similar effect to adding a form of regularization to the optimization process, potentially improving the model's generalization performance.

Although SGD is widely used, it has some limitations. Due to the random nature of mini-batch sampling, SGD may exhibit noisy convergence and slower convergence rate compared to batch gradient descent on convex loss functions. Techniques like momentum and adaptive learning rates (e.g., Adam, RMSprop) are often employed to address these issues and improve the stability and convergence properties of SGD.

Overall, Stochastic Gradient Descent is a popular and effective optimization algorithm for training machine learning models, particularly in scenarios with large datasets and complex models.

H. Stochastic Gradient Descent – Adam Method [18]:

Stochastic Gradient Descent with Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) is an optimization algorithm commonly used for training machine learning models, particularly in the field of deep learning. Adam combines the advantages of stochastic gradient descent with adaptive learning rate methods to achieve efficient and effective optimization.

The key characteristics of the Adam optimization algorithm are as follows:

- **Adaptive Learning Rates:** Adam adapts the learning rate for each model parameter individually, based on the historical gradient information. It computes individual learning rates that are proportional to the estimated first and second moments of the gradients. This adaptation allows Adam to automatically adjust the learning

rates for different parameters, leading to faster convergence and more stable optimization.

- **Momentum:** Adam incorporates the concept of momentum, which helps accelerate the optimization process and smooth out the noise in the gradient updates. It maintains a decaying moving average of past gradients, similar to the momentum term in other optimization algorithms. The momentum term allows Adam to persistently move in the direction of the gradients' history, enabling faster convergence and avoiding sharp changes in the parameter updates.
- **Bias Correction:** Adam performs bias correction during the initial iterations of training to address bias towards zero that occurs due to the initialization of the first and second moment estimations. This correction ensures better estimation accuracy and stability, especially at the beginning of the optimization process.
- **Parameter Initialization:** Adam requires initializing the first and second moment estimations and the momentum term. Typically, these values are initialized as zero vectors, which are gradually updated during the optimization process.
- **Hyperparameters:** Adam has hyperparameters that need to be set. The most important hyperparameters include the learning rate (controls the step size), the momentum decay rate (controls the memory of past gradients), and the first and second moment decay rates (control the weights given to past gradients).

Adam has proven to be an effective optimization algorithm for training deep neural networks. It combines the benefits of adaptive learning rates and momentum to achieve faster convergence and better optimization results. However, it is worth noting that selecting appropriate hyperparameters for Adam can be critical for optimal performance, and these hyperparameters may need to be tuned for different models and datasets.

Overall, Stochastic Gradient Descent with the Adam method is widely used and has become a popular choice for optimizing deep learning models, offering efficient convergence, adaptive learning rates, and momentum-based updates for improved optimization performance.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY:

Our primary aim for the project is to conduct an experimental study that centers around the comparison of five distinct algorithms utilized for emotion recognition based on facial expressions. The following diagram showcases the step-by-step progression of our study, commencing with data importation and proceeding through various stages until the testing phase, where we evaluate the best model and parameters derived from our comprehensive comparison.

Fig. 2. The pipeline of our experiment

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP:

Rescaling and resizing an image involves adjusting its dimensions while maintaining the original aspect ratio or modifying it as desired. This process consists of two main steps: scaling and resizing.

When scaling an image, the pixel values, which range from 0 to 255 and represent pixel intensity, are divided by 255. This scaling operation transforms the pixel values to a normalized range of 0 to 1. This normalization is commonly applied to ensure consistency and standardization of pixel values, which can be advantageous for various image processing algorithms and models.

In the context of facial expression recognition, resizing an image to (48, 48) is a common preprocessing step to prepare facial images for emotion recognition models. The dimensions of 48x48 pixels have been widely adopted in facial expression datasets and models. This size is typically sufficient to capture essential facial features while keeping the computational requirements manageable. By resizing the image to this specific dimension, it conforms to the input requirements of many facial expression recognition systems.

In summary, scaling an image involves normalizing its pixel values to a range between 0 and 1, while resizing refers to adjusting its dimensions. Resizing an image to (48, 48) is often performed in facial expression recognition to standardize the input size for emotion recognition models, striking a balance between capturing crucial facial details and computational efficiency.

```
def load_data(dir_path, IMG_SIZE):
    X = []
    y = []
    i = 0
    labels = dict()
    for path in tqdm(sorted(os.listdir(dir_path))):
        if not path.startswith('.'):
            labels[i] = path
            for file in os.listdir(dir_path + path):
                if not file.startswith('.'):
                    img = cv2.imread(dir_path + path + '/' + file)
                    img = img.astype('float32') / 255
                    resized = cv2.resize(img, IMG_SIZE, interpolation = cv2.INTER_AREA)
                    X.append(resized)
                    y.append(i)
            i += 1
    X = np.array(X)
    y = np.array(y)
    print(f'{len(X)} images loaded from {dir_path} directory.')
    return X, y, labels
```

Fig. 3. data importation

Loading a pre-trained model entails importing and initializing a pre-existing deep learning model that has

undergone training on a substantial dataset. This pre-trained model has already acquired meaningful representations from the data it was trained on, enabling it to perform specific tasks like image classification.

A pre-trained model on [ImageNet](#) specifically refers to a deep learning model that has undergone training on the expansive ImageNet dataset. The ImageNet dataset serves as a prominent benchmark in the field of computer vision, encompassing millions of labeled images that span thousands of distinct classes or categories.

```
VGG16=tf.keras.applications.VGG16(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=IMG_SIZE + (3,))
VGG19=tf.keras.applications.VGG19(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=IMG_SIZE + (3,))

ResNet50V2=tf.keras.applications.ResNet50V2(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=IMG_SIZE + (3,))

EfficientNetB0=tf.keras.applications.efficientnet.EfficientNetB0(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=IMG_SIZE + (3,))
EfficientNetB7=tf.keras.applications.efficientnet.EfficientNetB7(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=IMG_SIZE + (3,))
```

Fig. 4. Load the pre-trained models

Freezing refers to the process of preventing the weights and parameters of certain layers in a pre-trained model from being updated or further trained during the fine-tuning or transfer learning process.

When we load a pre-trained model, all the layers in the model have already undergone training on a large dataset to acquire meaningful representations. However, in certain scenarios, we may wish to fine-tune the model for a specific task using our own dataset.

By freezing layers, we preserve the learned representations, particularly in the early layers that capture fundamental features and patterns. This approach is advantageous because the pre-trained model has already been trained on a dataset that shares similarities with our task, and we aim to leverage this existing knowledge while fine-tuning the model on our specific data.

```
VGG16.trainable=False
VGG19.trainable=False
ResNet50V2.trainable=False
EfficientNetB0.trainable=False
EfficientNetB7.trainable=False
```

Fig. 5. Freezing layers

Keras Tuner is a powerful hyperparameter optimization library specifically designed for the Keras deep learning framework. It provides an intuitive and efficient way to search and tune hyperparameters to improve the performance of your deep learning models.

Hyperparameters are configuration settings that are not learned from the data during model training but are set before training begins. They determine the architecture, optimization algorithm, learning rate, number of layers, number of units in each layer, activation functions, dropout rates, and more.

Keras Tuner offers a user-friendly interface and various search algorithms to explore the hyperparameter space and find optimal or near-optimal combinations. Here are some key features and components of Keras Tuner:

- **Search Spaces:** Keras Tuner allows you to define search spaces for each hyperparameter, specifying the range, values, or distributions to be considered during the search process. This flexibility enables you to customize the search space according to your specific requirements.
- **Tuners:** Keras Tuner provides different tuners, including RandomSearch, Hyperband, and Bayesian Optimization-based tuners like BayesianOptimization and TPE (Tree-structured Parzen Estimators). These tuners use different search strategies to efficiently explore the hyperparameter space and identify the best combinations.
- **Objective Functions:** You can define an objective function to evaluate the performance of your model based on specific metrics such as accuracy, loss, or any custom evaluation metric. The tuner uses this objective function to guide the search process and optimize the hyperparameters accordingly.
- **Early Stopping:** Keras Tuner supports early stopping, allowing you to terminate the search process if the performance of the model plateaus or worsens. This feature helps save computational resources by stopping the search early if no further improvements are observed.
- **Visualization and Analysis:** Keras Tuner provides tools to visualize and analyze the results of the hyperparameter search, including the best hyperparameters found, performance metrics across different trials, and search history. These insights help you understand the impact of different hyperparameters on model performance.

By using Keras Tuner, you can automate the process of hyperparameter optimization, saving time and effort compared to manual trial and error. It empowers you to efficiently find the optimal hyperparameters for your deep learning models, improving their performance and generalization on a wide range of tasks.

Overall, Keras Tuner simplifies the process of hyperparameter optimization by providing a comprehensive framework to define search spaces, select search algorithms, define objective functions, and analyze the search results. It enables you to unlock the full potential of your deep learning models by finding the best hyperparameter configurations for your specific tasks and datasets.

```
def model_builder(hp):
    model = tf.keras.Sequential()
    model.add(tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(IMG_SIZE + (3,))))

    if hp.Choice('base_model', values=['VGG16', 'VGG19', 'EfficientNetB0', 'EfficientNetB7'])=='VGG16':
        model.add(VGG16)
    elif hp.Choice('base_model', values=['VGG16', 'VGG19', 'EfficientNetB0', 'EfficientNetB7'])=='VGG19':
        model.add(VGG19)
    elif hp.Choice('base_model', values=['VGG16', 'VGG19', 'EfficientNetB0', 'EfficientNetB7'])=='ResNet50V2':
        model.add(ResNet50V2)
    elif hp.Choice('base_model', values=['VGG16', 'VGG19', 'EfficientNetB0', 'EfficientNetB7'])=='EfficientNetB0':
        model.add(EfficientNetB0)
    else:
        model.add(EfficientNetB7)

    model.add(tf.keras.layers.Flatten())
    model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(1000, activation='relu'))
```

Fig. 6. Keras-tuner_1

```

if hp.Boolean('dropout_1'):
    model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dropout(rate=hp.Float(
        'dropout_12',
        min_value=0.0,
        max_value=0.5,
        default=0.25,
        step=0.05,
    )))

model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(6, activation='softmax'))

model.compile(
    optimizer=tf.keras.optimizers.Adam(
        hp.Float(
            'learning_rate',
            min_value=1e-4,
            max_value=1e-2,
            sampling='LOG',
            default=1e-3
        )
    ),
    loss='binary_crossentropy',
    metrics=["accuracy"])

```

Fig. 7. Keras-tuner_2

```
early_stopping = tf.keras.callbacks.EarlyStopping(monitor='val_loss', patience=4)
```

Fig. 8. Early Stopping

B. Results and decision:

The best model consists of the following components:

- **VGG16:** VGG16 is a widely used convolutional neural network architecture that has demonstrated excellent performance in image classification tasks. It consists of multiple convolutional and pooling layers, which learn hierarchical features from input images.
- **Flatten Layer:** The flatten layer is used to convert the multidimensional output of the convolutional layers into a one-dimensional feature vector. It allows the subsequent fully connected layers to process the learned features.
- **Dense Layer with 1000 Units:** This dense layer is a fully connected layer with 1000 units. Each unit represents a neuron that takes input from all the neurons in the previous layer. The dense layer learns and captures complex patterns and relationships in the extracted features.
- **Output Layer with Softmax Activation:** The output layer is another dense layer that contains 6 units, corresponding to the 6 classes in the classification problem. The softmax activation function is applied to this layer. The softmax function transforms the output of each unit into a probability distribution, where the values sum up to 1. It enables the model to predict the probability of each class, facilitating multiclass classification.

In summary, the best model incorporates the VGG16 architecture as the backbone, followed by a flatten layer to reshape the output, a dense layer with 1000 units to capture complex patterns, and an output layer with softmax

activation for multiclass classification. The softmax function plays a crucial role in converting the final layer's outputs into class probabilities.

```
best_model.summary()
```

```
Model: "sequential"
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
vgg16 (Functional)	(None, 1, 1, 512)	14714688
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 512)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 1000)	513000
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 6)	6006

```

=====
Total params: 15,233,694
Trainable params: 519,006
Non-trainable params: 14,714,688

```

Fig. 9. Best model

Fig. 10. The graphical representation depicting the loss and accuracy metrics

The confusion matrix offers a comprehensive overview of the model's performance by illustrating the distribution of accurate and inaccurate predictions across various classes. It aids in comprehending the specific types of errors made by the model, including false positives and false negatives. By examining the confusion matrix, one can gain insights into the model's strengths and weaknesses in correctly classifying different classes.

Fig. 11. Confusion matrix

VII. CONCLUSION:

In summary, this research study aimed to compare the performance of five different algorithms (VGG16, VGG19, RESNET50V2, EfficientNETB0, and EfficientB7) in recognizing emotions based on facial expressions. The study followed a systematic approach, starting from data importation and progressing through various stages to identify the best model and settings through comprehensive comparison.

The study's results provide valuable insights into the performance of these algorithms in emotion recognition. By assessing their accuracy and analyzing the confusion matrix, we determined the algorithm that performed best in recognizing emotions based on facial expressions.

These findings contribute to the advancement of emotion recognition technology and have potential applications in areas such as e-learning platforms and computer interactions. By employing the best model and settings identified in this study, we can enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of emotion recognition systems, resulting in improved user experiences and tailored support.

It is worth noting that further research can be conducted to explore alternative algorithms or enhance the existing ones. Additionally, real-life applications should consider factors like computational resources, complexity, and striking a balance between accuracy and efficiency.

Overall, this research serves as a foundation for future developments in emotion recognition based on facial expressions. It underscores the significance of selecting the most appropriate algorithm to achieve accurate and reliable results. By leveraging the findings of this study, we can advance emotion recognition technology and enhance human-computer interactions across various domains.

VIII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORKS:

A. Limitations:

- **Accuracy Improvement Needed:** The evaluated algorithms for emotion recognition based on facial expressions demonstrated limited accuracy in their results. There is a clear need for further enhancements to improve their performance and achieve higher levels of accuracy.
- **Dataset Limitations:** The dataset utilized for training and evaluation purposes may have had certain limitations. These limitations could include a small size or inadequate representation of the full range of emotions. Such constraints may have impacted the accuracy and generalizability of the algorithms' performance.
- **Algorithm Diversity:** The selection of five algorithms for testing may not encompass all potential options available for emotion recognition. Exploring and incorporating additional algorithms could potentially yield better outcomes and more comprehensive coverage of the problem domain.
- **Resource Requirements:** The evaluated algorithms may have demanding resource requirements, necessitating powerful computing systems equipped with high-performance graphics cards and processors. The availability and accessibility of such resources can pose challenges when deploying these algorithms in real-life applications.

Overall, these observations highlight the need for ongoing research and development in the field of emotion recognition from facial expressions. By addressing the limitations identified, such as accuracy, dataset quality, algorithm diversity, and resource requirements, we can advance the effectiveness and applicability of these algorithms in real-world scenarios.

B. Future Works:

- **Advancements in Algorithm Development:** There is a need for further research and development to create more sophisticated algorithms for emotion recognition based on facial expressions. Exploring innovative approaches, such as incorporating temporal or attention mechanisms, can potentially enhance the accuracy and robustness of these algorithms.
- **Expanded Dataset Collection:** The collection of larger and more diverse datasets that encompass a wide range of emotions and individuals is crucial. A more comprehensive dataset can improve the accuracy of the algorithms by providing a richer representation of real-world scenarios.
- **Real-life Testing and Validation:** Conducting thorough testing and validation of the algorithms in real-life settings, such as integrating them into e-learning platforms or other practical applications, is essential. This enables the algorithms to be evaluated in authentic contexts, providing valuable feedback for further improvements and fine-tuning.
- **Hybrid Approaches and Ensemble Techniques:** Exploring hybrid approaches that combine multiple algorithms or employing ensemble techniques can potentially yield improved accuracy in emotion

recognition. By leveraging the strengths of different algorithms and integrating their outputs, it is possible to achieve better overall performance.

- Personalized CNN Configuration: Customizing the configuration of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) specifically for emotion recognition can lead to improved accuracy and adaptability to different datasets. Tailoring the architecture, hyperparameters, and training strategies to the specific requirements of emotion recognition tasks can enhance the algorithms' performance.

In summary, future advancements in emotion recognition based on facial expressions should focus on algorithm development, dataset expansion, real-life testing, hybrid approaches, and personalized CNN configurations. These steps can lead to more accurate and reliable emotion recognition systems, enabling their effective integration into various applications and domains.

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